

ISic0733

I.Sicily inscription 0733

Language

Latin

Type

seat

inscription

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Amphitheatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro

Greco

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Stylized representation of a bireme below the writing line, on the lower right corner

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]RV[---]

Apparatus

Text after Buonocore 1992 (EAOR)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491623

EDCS 21900454

Bibliography

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